

Solvatochromic Behaviour of some 4,5-Dioxo-1-phenylpyrazoline Derivatives

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Manuscript received 23 September 1987, revised 11 July 1988, accepted 14 December 1988

The electronic absorption spectra of 4,5-dioxo-1-phenylpyrazoline compounds were recorded in organic solvents of different polarities, in mixtures of solvents and in buffer solutions. The longer wavelength band is assigned to intermolecular CT interaction. The spectra recorded in the CT complex region in mixed solvents revealed the formation of molecular complexes between the solute and EtOH, DMF, DMSO. The stability constant and heat of formation of these complexes have been determined. The basicity constants of the compounds are calculated and discussed.

PYRAZOLONE compounds find various industrial uses¹. In the biological field, pyrazolone compounds have been used as inhibitors of cell growth² and in anticancer treatment³.

But little work has been done on their spectral behaviour. Thus, we have chosen some 4,5-dioxopyrazoline compounds in order to study their spectral behaviour in pure organic solvents of different polarities, in solvents mixture and in buffer solutions of varying hydrogen ion concentrations. This spectral study may give some light on the practical application of these compounds.

Experimental

The compounds used were prepared as described earlier¹. The structure and purity of the compounds were checked by elemental analysis and ir spectra. The following compounds were prepared:

- 1, R=OH,
2, R=H
3, R=CHO

The solvents used were of spectral grade (B. D. H. or E. Merck). The electronic spectra were recorded on a Shimadzu 240 spectrophotometer at 25° using 1-cm matched silica cell. The modified universal buffer series of Britton and Robinson⁴ were prepared by mixing the 0.4 M acid mixture (phosphoric, acetic and boric acids) (150 ml) with the appropriate volume of 1.0 M NaOH. The acetate buffer solutions (pH=0.65–5.20) were prepared as recommended⁵, by mixing 1.0 M sodium acetate (50 ml) with appropriate volume of

1.0 M HCl. The pH values were checked using a Digital MV pH-meter accurate to ± 0.05 pH units.

Results and Discussion

Band assignments: The absorption spectra of the pyrazolone compounds (1–4) in pure organic solvents of various polarities, viz. EtOH, CCl₄, CHCl₃, DMF and DMSO were recorded (Table 1). Spectra of the compounds in ethanol are characterised by three bands except for compound 4, which exhibit an extra fourth band at longer wavelength.

The two uv bands located at 205–212 and 242–265 nm can be ascribed to the $\pi-\pi^*$ transition in each of the pyrazole ring and 1-phenyl ring of the compound respectively. This assignment is confirmed by little influence of the position of these two bands by changing the nature of the substituent (R). These two bands do not appear in the other organic solvents used due to the perturbation effect of these solvents in this spectral region.

The third band at 320–395 nm can be assigned to $n-\pi^*$ transition influenced by possible intramolecular CT interaction. This is due to the excitation of n -electrons of each oxygen atoms of carbonyl groups and the nonquaternary pyrazolone nitrogen atom. The above assignment is substantiated by considering the spectra of the compounds in aqueous solutions of varying pH's. However, the intensity of this band decreases with red-shift in its position on increasing pH of the medium. This can be ascribed to the deprotonation of the nitrogen and oxygen atoms of the compound as the pH is increased; so an easier CT interaction is expected to occur through the whole solute molecule. The blue-shift is observed in this band in EtOH relative to the nonpolar solvents (CCl₄, CHCl₃). This reflects the role played by ethanol as a proton donor solvent, which can interact with the nitrogen and oxygen atoms of the solute mole-

TABLE 1—ELECTRONIC SPECTRAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 1-4 IN PURE ORGANIC SOLVENTS (λ_{max} , (nm); ϵ_{max} , $\times 10^{-3}$ mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹)

Compd. no.	EtOH		CCl ₄		CHCl ₃		DMF		DMSO	
	λ_{max}	ϵ_{max}	λ_{max}	ϵ_{max}	λ_{max}	ϵ_{max}	λ_{max}	ϵ_{max}	λ_{max}	ϵ_{max}
1	212	24.85	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
	265	18.50	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
	365	8.45	395	14.95	390	15.25	280b	8.55	285b	6.45
2	210	21.94	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
	258	15.04	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
	349	10.70	385	16.43	373	16.49	293	7.30	308	10.25
3	208	21.43	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
	258	15.04	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
	335	6.36	368	13.98	354	14.08	348	14.10	345	12.05
4	205	29.91	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
	242	16.29	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
	320	9.04	360	13.13	350	12.09	290	5.19	290	5.86
	435	13.45	—	—	—	—	335	10.00	338	10.19
							475	4.85	510	7.50

cule through intermolecular hydrogen bond as represented below.

Such interaction will result in the blocking of the solute non-bonding electrons and an expected difficult charge transfer through the molecule, i.e. high excitation energy is required and blue-shift is observed to CT band (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Electronic spectra of the 1×10^{-4} M of compound 4 in various organic solvents: (a) ethanol, (b) CCl₄, (c) CHCl₃, (d) DMF, and (e) DMSO.

The extra band observed at longer wavelength in the spectra of compound 4 in each of DMF (475 nm) and DMSO (510 nm), can be ascribed to the formation of solvated complex through an intermolecular H-bond⁶. This band is presumably due to intermolecular CT transition, where the CT force plays an important role in hydrogen bond formation⁷. This involves an electron transfer of the solute nitrogen and oxygen atoms to the antibonding orbital of O-H and H-C=O bonds of EtOH

and DMF or DMSO respectively. However, the location of this band at longer wavelength is due to the high stabilisation of the polar excited state of this transition (O-H...O) by the high polar DMF, DMSO solvents. Furthermore, the possibility of the formation of a H-bonding solvated complex with EtOH, DMF and DMSO molecules rather than with CCl₄ and CHCl₃, is due to the low ionisation potential of the former solvents relative to the latter ones. This in turn results in an easier formation of H-bonded solvated complex with EtOH, DMF and DMSO.

Spectra in mixed organic solvents: This study was performed in order to test the possibility of the formation of a hydrogen bonded molecular complex between the solute and the proton acceptor solvent molecules. Thus, the spectral behaviour of compound 4 in CCl₄ and CHCl₃ as solvents, each containing successively increasing amounts of EtOH, DMF and DMSO, was studied. On adding the polar solvent, a new band at longer wavelength appears where the band absorbance increases as the molarity of the solvent is increased. At the same time, the absorbance of the shorter wavelength band decreases and a fine isosbestic point is obtained (Fig. 2 as representative). This behaviour indicates that EtOH, DMF and DMSO molecules have great tendency to form solvated complexes with solute molecules and there is equilibrium between the solvated complex and the free solute molecules,

The value of molecular complex formation constant (K_f) is determined from the variation of absorbance obtained by increasing the polar solvent concentration at a given wavelength. The equation⁸ applied is

$$\log C = -\frac{1}{n} \log K_f + \frac{1}{n} \log \frac{(A - A_0)}{(A_1 - A)}$$

where, C is concentration of polar solvent, A_1 the absorbance in a high-polar solvent, A_0 the absorbance in a low-polar solvent, A the absorbance in a

Fig. 2. Electronic spectra of the 1×10^{-4} M of compound 4 in EtOH-CHCl₃ mixtures: (a) pure CHCl₃, (b) 1.72 M EtOH, (c) 3.43 M EtOH, (d) 5.15 M EtOH, (e) 6.87 M EtOH, (f) 8.59 M EtOH, (g) 10.30 M EtOH, (h) 12.02 M EtOH and (i) 17.17 M EtOH.

mixed solvent, and n the number of associated solvent molecules. The free energy of formation (ΔG) of the solvated complex is obtained from the relation,

$$\Delta G = -RT \ln K_f$$

The values of n , K_f and ΔG of the complexes liable to exist in solution are given in Table 2. It is

TABLE 2—VALUES OF K_f AND $-\Delta G$ FOR DIFFERENT SOLVATED COMPLEXES OF COMPOUND 4

System	n	$\log K_f$	K_f	$-\Delta G$ kcal mol ⁻¹ (25°)
EtOH-CCl ₄	3.6	0.81	6.46	1.098
EtOH-OHCl ₃	3.3	0.77	5.89	1.044
DMF-CCl ₄	3.05	0.78	6.03	1.057
DMF-OHCl ₃	2.8	0.76	5.75	1.090
DMSO-CCl ₄	3.4	0.79	6.17	1.071
DMSO-OHCl ₃	2.7	0.75	5.62	1.017

evident that the ability of EtOH, DMF and DMSO solvents to form a solvated molecular complex with compound 4 molecules is independent on the nature of the low-polarity solvent. Also, the complexes are formed through a weak intermolecular H-bond and have stoichiometric ratio $\sim 1:3$ (solute : solvent).

Determination of basicity constant: This work was undertaken with the intention of eliciting some information on the acid-base properties of the pyrazolone compounds under investigation. This is also relevant to the assignment of the bands observed in the visible region, especially to the charge transfer bands. The basicity constants were determined by considering the spectral shift of these compounds in the buffer solutions. Acetate buffer solutions are used to the lower values (pH=0.8-5.5) and universal buffer solution to the higher ones (pH=6.0-11.5). However, the spectra of the compounds

are characterised by two isosbestic points, revealing the existence of more than one equilibrium state between the protonated and non-protonated forms of these compounds.

The absorbance-pH curves obtained for compounds at selected wavelengths show a clear S-shape with two deflections. This behaviour indicates that two equilibria character exist. The first belongs to the protonation of nonquaternary nitrogen atom and the second to the two oxygen atoms of the carbonyl groups, which are dissociated simultaneously in one step.

The pK_1 and pK_2 values were determined using the half-height, limiting absorbance and the modified Colleter methods^{8,9}. The mean values are recorded in Table 3. The results show that the protonation

TABLE 3—MEAN pK_1 AND pK_2 VALUES OF COMPOUNDS 1-4

Compd. no.	pK_1	pK_2
1	3.75	7.88
2	3.70	7.91
3	3.44	7.65
4	3.01	7.01

of the nitrogen atom occurs at lower pH than the protonation of the oxygen atoms. This behaviour is presumably due to the formation of a solvated complex between the oxygen atoms of the solute and the water molecules through H-bonds, which lead to a high residual negative charge on the oxygen atoms and delays the equilibrium system. The pK_1 and pK_2 values are slightly dependent on the electron-nature of the substituent (R). Generally, the values of the basicity constants increase as the electron-donating character of the substituent (R) is increased. This is due to the easier CT transition towards the nonquaternary nitrogen atom and consequently to the carbonyl oxygen atoms.

References

- A. I. KORAIEM, *J. Prakt. Chem.*, 1984, 4, 695; 1984, 5, 811; P. K. JESTHI, M. BAY and S. K. MOHAPATRA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1978, 55, 712; N. S. KOZLOV, O. D. ZHIKHAREVA and S. A. BATISCHE, *Khm. Geterotskko Soedin.*, 1972, 12, 1619; A. P. CENTOLELLA, J. W. NELSON and H. G. KOLLOP, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1943, 65, 209; J. WILLIAMS and V. VANDENBERGHE, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1960, 54, 22657; K. K. MOHAMED, Ph. D. Thesis, Assiut University, Egypt, 1979.
- S. ZIGMAN and P. J. GILMAN, *Science*, 1980, 188, 4440.
- K. UCHIUMI and S. YASUI, *Jpn. Kokai Tokyo*, 1979, 79, 889.
- H. T. S. BRITTON, "Hydrogen Ions", 2nd. ed., Chapman and Hall, London, 1952, p. 365.
- H. T. S. BRITTON, "Hydrogen Ions", 4nd. ed., Chapman and Hall, London, 1956, p. 363.
- M. R. MAHMOUD, H. S. EL-KASHIF and R. ABD EL-HAMID, *Spectrochim. Acta (A)*, 1981, 37, 519.
- N. MATAGA and T. KUBICITA, "Molecular Interaction and Electronic Spectra", Marcel Dekker, New York, 1970.
- B. M. ISSA, M. M. GHONEIM, K. A. IDRIS and A. A. HARFOUSH, *Z. Phys. Chem.*, 1975, 94, 135.
- J. C. COLLETER, *J. Ann. Chem.*, 1960, 5, 415.